

Ride 2Rail

D6.1 Project visual identity & website

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Consortium of partners

PARTNER	COUNTRY
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FIT CONSULTING	Italy
OLTIS GROUP	Czech Republic
FSTECH	Italy
CEFRIEL	Italy
CERTH	Greece
EURNEX	Germany
EURECAT	Spain
POLIMI	Italy
UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE	United Kingdom
UNIFE	Belgium
UIC	France
UNIZA	Slovakia
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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, 'D6.1 Project identity & website', describes the objectives, structure, and look and feel of the RIDE2RAIL logo, visual charter, roll-up, website and Twitter account. All of these tools are essential to reach project objectives in regards to communication, including strengthening the project's identity, raising awareness and disseminating project developments to key stakeholders and external actors.

2. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CFM	Calls for Members
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
OC	Open Call
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
S2R JU	Shift2Rail Joint Undertaking
TL	Technical leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

3. BACKGROUND

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D6.1 “Project visual identity & website” in the framework of WP6, task 6.1 of the RIDE2RAIL project.

4. OBJECTIVES/AIM

The objectives of the RIDE2RAIL communication activities are to raise awareness about the project to a wide audience, to disseminate project developments to key stakeholders, to organise key project events, and finally to implement and update an appropriate online presence (website, social media). The RIDE2RAIL visual identity, roll-up, social media channels, and website are tools developed to reach these objectives.

The project logo and an accompanying graphic identity (which includes project colours and fonts) have been developed to establish a strong project identity. A strong identity ensures recognition among stakeholders and consistency in communication activities, and positions the RIDE2RAIL project as a strong brand. The project logo will be a returning visual throughout the whole project: it will be visible on the project brochure, on the roll-up, in presentation templates, and on all other forms of communication material developed by the RIDE2RAIL project.

To further support project communication, the RIDE2RAIL Twitter account and website will serve as the project's main gateways to reach target groups outside the consortium. The RIDE2RAIL website will be regularly updated in order to provide an up to date picture of the project, report the latest developments and announce upcoming events. The Twitter account will be used as a tool to expand outreach to a wide audience including end-users, and provide content about the project, the sector, or relevant events.

5. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

5.1. Logo and symbol

The RIDE2RAIL logo was developed in February 2020 by the UITP graphic designer after a dedicated briefing about the project. As can be seen in Figure 1, the RIDE2RAIL logo consists of a modern design due to innovative colour use and form. As of the innovative nature of the project, the colours that were chosen deviate from the 'standard' colours that are often seen in projects, such as green combined with blue. The flowing line in the logo resembles the switch from ride-sharing to rail (or public transport services in general), which is the core of the project.

In addition to a project logo, an icon was developed to support project visual identity. This icon can be, alike the logo, used on different communication materials, especially in cases where the logo's size would be too large for proper use. For example, the RIDE2RAIL icon has been used in the project's document templates.

Figure 1: RIDE2RAIL logo

Figure 2: RIDE2RAIL icon

5.2. Graphic charter

To further support project identity, a full graphic charter has been developed, consisting of project colours and fonts. It also includes various other visuals, such as a banner and background, which can be used in different dissemination tools, such as the project newsletters. The graphic charter has been sent to all project partners, to ensure consistent use of visuals throughout the project.

Figure 3: RIDE2RAIL banner

5.3. Templates

To ensure consistent use of the RIDE2RAIL logo and colours, various templates have been developed: a PowerPoint template, a deliverable template, a meeting minutes template, and a meeting agenda template. All consortium partners are encouraged to make use of these templates when presenting the RIDE2RAIL project in internal or external meetings.

Figure 4: RIDE2RAIL PowerPoint template

5.4. Roll-up

A project roll-up has been created as another means to strengthen the RIDE2RAIL identity. The roll-up has been designed in accordance with the project's colours and fonts. It was chosen to not disclose too

much information on the roll-up, as it should rather serve as a teaser that encourages people to visit the website. The RIDE2RAIL roll-up will be displayed at events RIDE2RAIL is organising or presenting at.

Figure 5: RIDE2RAIL roll-up

5.5. Guidelines

Finally, all RIDE2RAIL partners have received a document consisting of a set of recommendations and rules how to communicate about the RIDE2RAIL project, including how to use the project logo, how to correctly include EU and Shift2Rail mentioning, and what the process around publications on RIDE2RAIL entails.

6. WEBSITE

The RIDE2RAIL website can be accessed via <http://ride2rail.eu/>. It was launched on 26 March 2020. The website is composed of seven different sections:

- Home: this page provides an overview of the project and links tot other pages within the website. The homepage also includes the News & Events feed, and a slider including all logos from project partners;
- About: on this page, visitors can find the most information on the project. Alongside core info (budget, duration, etc.), it includes the objectives of the project and its vision. It also elaborates on how RIDE2RAIL fits in to the Shift2Rail and IP4 context;
- Pilots: here visitors can get a glimpse of the demos within the project, including their location and general objectives. This page will be updated at a later stage, when more input on the pilots is gathered;
- Partners: this page includes all the logos of the project partners as well as links to their websites;
- Library: in this part of the website, (public) project publications, deliverables and presentations will be uploaded at a later stage;
- News & Events: to keep visitors up to date with project developments and activities, regular news items will be posted on this page;
- Contact us: this page includes the contact details of the Project Coordinator.

Figure 6: homepage of the RIDE2RAIL website

Figure 7: a news-item on the RIDE2RAIL website

Users of the website can access the private area (Cooperation Tool) via a header in the menu. The website also includes a social media button that takes visitors to the RIDE2RAIL Twitter account. Furthermore, on every page, users have the possibility to subscribe to the RIDE2RAIL newsletter.

The footer displays the EU flag and Shift2Rail logo, and grant agreement number, and the full menu of the website. It also includes a link to the RIDE2RAIL cookie policy.

The website will be available up to five years after the project ends (in May 2022). This means that the website will also serve as a depository and a reference point for project related information and deliverables after the end of RIDE2RAIL, supporting in this way the dissemination and exploitation strategies of the project.

7. SOCIAL MEDIA

Twitter is one of the most well-known social media worldwide and is used in the RIDE2RAIL project to support reaching an audience as big as possible. A Twitter account for the project was created in March 2020 (@RIDE2RAIL).

Figure 8: RIDE2RAIL Twitter account

Content shared on the RIDE2RAIL Twitter timeline will often be related to events, publications, or interesting developments within the project or the public transport sector. Tweets on the RIDE2RAIL account are posted regularly to increase engagement with the audience. The ultimate goal of the RIDE2RAIL Twitter account is to gather a high-level audience of professional and industry experts with an interest in the project objectives.

8. CONCLUSIONS

By developing a logo, visual identity, roll-up, Twitter account and project website early in the RIDE2RAIL project, essential steps towards a coherent and consistent project identity have been made.

By consistently using the RIDE2RAIL visual features, the project will gain recognition among relevant stakeholders and become a solid brand. Furthermore, by developing the RIDE2RAIL social media and website and regularly updating these with relevant news, events, and articles, constant interaction with relevant stakeholders will be ensured.

By actively using these communication means, the project aims to build a strong relationship with the RIDE2RAIL target groups and increase engagement among them.